

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

EFFECT OF pH ON THE ANAEROBIC FERMENTATION OF FRUIT/VEGETABLES AND DISPOSABLE NAPPIES HYDROLYSATE FOR BIO-HYDROGEN PRODUCTION

Konstantina Tsigkou¹, Panagiota Tsafrakidou², Sofia Athanasopoulou¹, Constantina Zafiri², Michael Kornaros*¹

¹ *Laboratory of Biochemical Engineering and Environmental Technology (LBEET), Department of Chemical Engineering, University of Patras, University Campus, Patras, 26504, Greece*

² *Green Technologies Ltd, 5 Ellinos Stratiotou Str., Patras, 26223, Greece*

*Corresponding author. Tel.: +30 2610 997418; Fax: +30 2610 969584

E-mail address: kornaros@chemeng.upatras.gr (M. Kornaros)

Acknowledgments

The authors gratefully acknowledge the financial support of this study by the European Commission - Executive Agency for Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (EASME) - Project WASTE4THINK (H2020 - GA 688995) “Moving towards Life Cycle Thinking by integrating Advanced Waste Management Systems”.

Abstract

- **Purpose:** The objective of this work was to optimize the anaerobic fermentation of a mixed waste stream, consisted of fruit and vegetables (FVW) that have lost their marketing value and a disposable nappies' hydrolysate (DN). More specifically, the aim was to identify the optimal pH value for maximum hydrogen production and valuable metabolites such as volatile fatty acids and ethanol.
- **Methods:** A wide range of pH values was tested (from 4.5 to 7.5 with 0.5 increment) using an automatic controller system, in batch fermentations that took place in mesophilic temperature conditions (37 °C). The first set of experiments was carried out with the FVW mixture, diluted with water (2:3 v/v) and subsequent trials followed using a FVW mixture with DN hydrolysate at the same ratio (2:3 v/v).
- **Results:** The maximum hydrogen volume was produced at pH 6.0 (1.34 L H₂/L_{Reactor}), for the fruit/vegetable stream whereas, the maximum concentration of ethanol and volatile fatty acids (15.60 g/L) was reached at pH 6.5 for the same substrate. Regarding the mixed waste stream, both hydrogen production and metabolites concentration reached a maximum at pH 7.5 with 4.09 L H₂/L_{Reactor} and 17.16 g/L respectively.
- **Conclusions:** Different optimum pH value for bio-hydrogen production was observed between the anaerobic fermentation of the two substrates (FVW and FVW/DN hydrolysate mixture). Higher overall yields and concentrations of the metabolic products were obtained with the fermentation of the mixed substrate.

Statement of novelty

Disposable nappies represent a significant amount of municipal solid wastes that are currently sent to landfills, and their organic content remains thus unexploited. Up to date, there are limited research attempts and practical applications that use this waste stream as a source to produce added value products, besides compost. The present study provides quantitative data relating co-digestion of used disposable nappies and fruit/vegetables with pH effect on bio-hydrogen production. As such, it helps the better understanding of this waste stream regarding its valorization through anaerobic digestion for the production of gaseous bio-fuels and/or other metabolites. In addition, optimization of an important factor such as pH, is a useful tool for the successful design of scale-up processes, concerning the same substrates.

Keywords: biohydrogen, disposable nappies, food waste, anaerobic fermentation, pH effect

1- INTRODUCTION

1
2 Energy crisis as a result of fossil fuel stocks decline, rising fuel prices due to high demand and the dependence of all
3 production processes on fuels, in combination with climate change, have incited researchers globally for alternative
4 sustainable energy sources that could offer a solution to these concerns. Among the eco-friendly biofuels, hydrogen (H₂) is
5 the most promising due to its high energy yield (122 kJ/g) on mass basis, which is almost three times greater than that from
6 hydrocarbon fuels, and high cleanness, since only water vapour is produced from its combustion [1–3]. H₂ is currently
7 produced via conventional water electrolysis and thermo-catalytic reformation using natural gas and oil. These processes
8 though, are characterized by a high greenhouse-gas footprint which is a contradiction from an environmental point view,
9 considering that the scope is to produce a cleaner fuel [4, 5].

10
11 Dark or anaerobic fermentation (AF) is a practical method for bio-hydrogen production, consuming less energy than
12 physicochemical ones. Metabolic pathways of facultative or obligate anaerobic bacteria, lead to bio-hydrogen production
13 through the decomposition of organic carbon from various feedstock substrates. Besides bio-hydrogen, volatile fatty acids
14 (VFAs) and ethanol can be also produced, as by-products of the process, which may be further utilized for methane, biodiesel
15 and bio-plastics synthesis [2], among other uses. Anaerobic fermentation can be also considered as a waste management
16 method, since organic wastes and wastewaters are treated and biologically processed this way, tackling the environmental
17 burden of waste disposal [6].

18
19 Promising results of biological hydrogen production have been obtained using different substrates. Municipal solid wastes
20 [7], cellulose containing wastes [8], agroindustrial wastewaters [9], cheese whey [10], food waste [11] as well as used nappies
21 [12], have been recently reported as potential substrates for AF, taking into account that the type of substrate is of crucial
22 importance for the effective H₂ production.

23
24 Almost 1.5 billion tons of food waste is being disposed annually around the globe, which accounts for the 33% of the food
25 production for human consumption [6]. In Greece, large Super Market chains, return most of the expired food products or
26 products of low quality (i.e. meat, fish, pasta, milk etc) to the production companies for waste management or lead it to
27 animal food companies and social actions against poverty. Fruit and vegetables, due to their vulnerability, are being thrown
28 away and led to landfilling. Interestingly, food waste is rich in carbohydrates and other nutrients and therefore could be
29 utilized in fermentation-based bio-refining processes for the production of biofuels and/or added value products [5].

30
31 Disposable nappies are primarily composed of cellulose and synthetic fibres that can be treated by biological methods.
32 According to EDANA [13] a typical composition of a disposable baby nappy is 36.6% cellulose pulp, 30.7% sodium
33 polyacrylate (SAP), 16% polypropylene, 6.2% low-density polyethylene, and 10.5% of elastic and adhesive tapes. Cellulosic
34 content is not the only biodegradable material that could be valorized from a used disposable nappy. The percentage of

1 organic content can reach almost 87% if urine and excreta are also added [14]. To date, the aforementioned recyclable
2 materials and potential energy sources of this waste stream, are disposed of to landfills or led to incineration, due to collection
3 of nappies with unsorted Municipal Solid Wastes (MSW) [15–17]. In the USA, 3.4 million tones of nappies are produced
4 each year and more than 90% is sent to landfills [17].
5

6
7 Increasing living standards, consumerism and throw-away mentality, combined with unsustainable waste disposal practices
8 have led to increased waste amounts in landfills. Landfilling is responsible for health hazards, fires and explosions,
9
10 vegetation damage, unpleasant odors, landfill settlement, ground water pollution, air pollution, and global warming owing
11
12 to the fact that biogas and leachate migrates away from the landfill boundaries and are released into the surrounding
13
14 environment [18, 19]. Development of sustainable and effective waste valorization is mandatory to circumvent waste
15
16 disposal and environmental problems.
17

18
19 This work aimed at assessing the effect of pH on the anaerobic fermentation of a mixed waste stream, consisted of fruit and
20
21 vegetables (FVW), that cannot be consumed or are considered low quality from food suppliers, and a used disposable
22
23 nappies' hydrolysate (DN). More specifically, the purpose was to identify the optimal pH value for maximum bio-hydrogen
24
25 production and valuable metabolites such as VFAs and ethanol. According to literature, pH regulation plays an important
26
27 role on the final performance of AF. Even narrow changes of pH in the bioreactor, affect significantly the microbial balance,
28
29 metabolic pathways and consequently the metabolic products. In general, acidic pH < 4 favors the accumulation of acidic
30
31 metabolites and ethanol and inhibits H₂ production [20], while at pH > 7 propionate is predominant and H₂ synthesis is
32
33 limited. Thus, it is crucial to maintain pH constant at an optimum value to maximize H₂ productivity [2, 9]. It should be
34
35 noted that optimum pH for H₂ production, varies depending on the fermented substrate and therefore must be determined
36
37 accordingly [21]. In the present study, constant pH, varying from 4.5 to 7.5, was studied in batch experiments at mesophilic
38
39 conditions, with FVW and a mixture of FVW and DN hydrolysate as fermentation feedstocks.
40
41
42
43

44 **2- MATERIALS AND METHODS**

45 **2.1 Anaerobic sludge**

46
47 Anaerobic sludge, obtained from a municipal wastewater treatment plant in Metamorphosis (Attiki, Greece), was used as
48
49 inoculum at 15% v/v for all batch experiments. The sludge was boiled at 100 °C for 20 min, prior to experiments, in order
50
51 to enrich hydrogen-producing bacteria via the deactivation of methanogens and H₂ consumers [22]. The total solids (TS)
52
53 content of the sludge was 15.6±3.6 g/L, with 70±2 % of it being volatile solids (VS).
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

2.2 Fermentation substrates

Fruit and vegetables, that did not meet quality standards for the supply chain, were collected from a Super Market in Patras (Achaia, Greece). Hard pieces like stalks, were removed and the rest were pulped, mixed and homogenized with an analytical mill (Sigma-Aldrich, IKA A11).

Used disposable nappies were collected from a private nursery in Chalandri (Attica, Greece). The disposable nappies were cut manually with scissors and the process described by Conway et al. [23] was followed in order to obtain a hydrolysate with the containing cellulose and excreta.

Both FVW and DN hydrolysate, were stored separately at -18 °C until further processing.

2.3 Experimental set-up and procedure

All experiments were performed in 1-L double wall, cylindrical, stainless steel (INOX 316) bioreactors with a working volume of 750 mL at constant conditions. Temperature was controlled via a thermocouple and was maintained at 37 ± 0.2 °C using hot water circulation. A motor drive unit, on the top of the bioreactor, reserved continuous stirring. pH was automatically controlled (HACH controller, SC200) and kept constant with the addition of 0.5N NaOH solution through a peristaltic pump. The range of pH values tested was 4.5-7.5, using a step of 0.5 for the FVW substrate (diluted with tap water at 2:3 v/v ratio). Subsequently, batch experiments with FVW and DN hydrolysate at a 2:3 v/v ratio were conducted. The second set of experiments tested only the pH values that considered to produce adequate amounts of bio-hydrogen and VFAs. A total of four (4) pH values were tested in the mixture of FVW and DN hydrolysate, namely 6.0, 6.5, 7.0 and 7.5. A mixture of N₂/CO₂ gases at 80/20 % v/v ratio was used to purge the headspace of bioreactors, to ensure an initial anaerobic environment. In **Fig. 1a** the schematic diagram of experimental methodology followed for the batch tests using FVW and DN hydrolysate, is presented. **Fig. 1b** depicts the experimental apparatus used for the batch tests process. It should be noted that each experiment lasted until the end of the metabolites' production (96-140h).

2.4 Analytical Methods

Physicochemical characterization of the used substrates, as well as chemical analysis of the effluents from the bioreactor, were performed. During the experiments, samples were taken in order to determine the composition of the produced biogas, other metabolites such as VFAS, lactic acid and ethanol as well as total and dissolved COD (t-COD and d-COD), total and dissolved carbohydrates, TSS and VSS. Samples were taken every 4-6 hours according to the evolution of the experiment. Off-line pH measurements were conducted using an electrode (Thermo Scientific, Orion ROSS Ultra Refillable pH/ATC Triode), while alkalinity, TS, VS, TSS, VSS, t-COD, d-COD, TKN, ammonium nitrogen, total and dissolved phosphorus

1 were determined according to *Standard Methods* [24]. Total and dissolved carbohydrates were measured according to
2 Joseffson [25], phenolic compounds were determined according to Waterman and Mole [26], and VFAs as well as ethanol
3 were analysed on a gas chromatograph (Agilent Technologies, 7890A) equipped with a flame ionization detector, as
4 described by Dareioti et al. [9]. Lactic acid was measured with a DIONEX IC300 ion chromatography system using a
5 thermostated (30 °C) Dionex IonPac analytical column (AS19 length 4 x250 mm and 7.5 mm I.D), a guard column (4 x 50
6 mm length and 12 mm I.D) and an electron conductivity detector (Dionex). Fats and Oils were measured after extraction
7 with hexane using a Soxhlet extractor (Velp Scientifica, SER 148). All experiments were carried out in triplicate. A custom-
8 made equipment was used for the total biogas and bio-hydrogen volume quantification. The apparatus is composed of a U-
9 tube filled with engine oil, an electron valve and a counter. The volume of gases is measured by counting the number of
10 displacements of constant oil volume. Biogas composition analysis was performed by gas chromatography with a capillary
11 column (HP-PLOT/Q, 30 m in length, 0.53 mm I.D. and 40 µm packing film), a thermal conductivity detector (TCD) and
12 nitrogen as carrier gas. Biogas production was converted to standard conditions (i.e. STP = 0 °C and 1 atm).
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25

26 **3- RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

27 **3.1 Physicochemical characterization of fermentation substrates**

28 Samples of the fermentation substrates were taken throughout the experimentation period, and measured in triplicate, in
29 order to determine their characteristics and ensure that the batch tests are performed with constant feedstock. As shown in
30 **Table 1**, DN hydrolysate is characterized by a neutral to alkaline pH (7.73 ± 0.04), which can be attributed to water and the
31 presence of urine that has a high pH value when stored, due to the decomposition of urea and urate [27]. In general, pH of
32 food waste is characterized as acidic with values close to 5.0 [28]; in this case pH of FVW is more acidic (3.48 ± 0.30) and
33 therefore the resulting mixture of FVW/DN hydrolysate ends up with pH 4.67 ± 0.18 . Furthermore, FVW presents high
34 organic content, which is mainly attributed to the total carbohydrates concentration of this waste stream (64.53 ± 7.46 g/kg
35 ww). Total solids (TS) of FVW is also high (111.55 ± 3.99 g/kg ww) with 90.5% of it being volatile solids (VS), and
36 COD:N:P ratio is 303:4.5:1.
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48

49 Regarding DN hydrolysate, the absence of soluble carbohydrates leads to the conclusion that cellulosic fibers from the
50 nappies are the main source of carbohydrates. Although the biodegradable content of a used nappy is considerable (cellulose
51 fibers plus excreta), yet DN hydrolysate presents rather low concentrations of nutrients and organic carbon. This result is
52 due to the high dilution ratio, that is needed for the pre-treatment. The latter has an impact on the TS as well, which is rather
53 low (8.07 ± 0.97 g/kg ww).
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

1
2 Finally, the mixture FVW/DN hydrolysate has lower organic load than FVW, due to its dilution with the hydrolysate and its
3 COD:N:P ratio is 317.5:6:1, which is almost ideal considering that for anaerobic processes the optimum operational ratio is
4 350:7:1 [29].
5
6

7 8 **3.2 Effect of pH on FVW anaerobic fermentation**

9
10 Batch experiments with FVW diluted with tap water at 2:3 v/v ratio were conducted. The range of pH values tested was 4.5-
11 7.5, using a step of 0.5. The volume of produced biogas as well as its composition was analysed throughout the experiments.
12
13 Other parameters such as, VFAs and ethanol, lactic acid, t-Carbohydrates, d-Carbohydrates, t-COD, d-COD, TSS and VSS
14 were determined at regular basis, in order to monitor the process.
15
16

17
18 Biogas production at STP conditions, is depicted in **Fig. 2a**. In all cases, biogas was composed of H₂ and CO₂, while CH₄
19 was not detected. At pH 4.5 and 5.0 there was practically no H₂, since acidic conditions inhibit metabolic activities related
20 with H₂ production [2, 30, 31]. Maximum H₂ volume and yield (1008.1 ml, 1.345 L H₂/ L_{Reactor}) was obtained at pH 6.0, in
21 accordance with researchers that investigated the effect of pH on H₂ production with different substrates in batch experiments
22 [9, 32]. At pH 7.0 and 7.5 though, H₂ volume prevailed CO₂, constituting 56.2% and 78.1% respectively of the total biogas
23 volume obtained. VFAs and ethanol production (**Fig. 2b**) is a useful tool for the assessment of the process and information
24 can be extracted regarding the H₂ yields, since acidogenesis and H₂ generation are closely related. At pH 4.5, acetic acid and
25 ethanol were mainly produced, and their concentrations reached 1,683.77 and 1,380.94 mg/L respectively, with the rest of
26 the VFAs concentrations being less than 40 mg/L. Lactic acid appeared at pH 5.0, having a high concentration (4,681.94
27 mg/L), even though it was expected at lower pH values as well, according to literature [32, 33]. Lactate concentration was
28 followed by acetic acid (1,468.06 mg/L) and ethanol (1,093.75 mg/L). Various intermediate metabolites were produced at
29 pH 5.5. Acetic acid (2,135.90 mg/L) and ethanol (2,197.59 mg/L) were predominant at the end of the fermentation, while
30 lactic acid was also produced but was not detected after 39.2h. Caproic acid appeared at 54.3h of fermentation and butyrate
31 at 68h. Their concentrations reached 340.63 and 732.84 mg/L respectively. Isobutyrate and isovalerate were less than 85
32 mg/L, while propionate concentration was 684.40 mg/L. Total VFAs and ethanol production of 10,199.47 mg/L was obtained
33 at pH 6.0, where the highest H₂ production was also observed, as stated previously. At the same pH value, butyrate had the
34 highest concentration (6,262.82 mg/L), which is in agreement with literature [34] where it is mentioned that butyric and
35 acetic acid type fermentations result in higher H₂ production. Zhang et al. [35] also reported butyric acid as the predominant
36 VFA at pH 6.0, in kitchen waste anaerobic fermentation experiments. Acetic acid reached its maximum concentration
37 (12,216.46 mg/L) at pH 6.5 followed by propionic and butyric acid with 1,210.98 and 1,500.01 mg/L respectively. Lower
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

1 concentrations of acetic acid and butyric acid are noticed at pH 7.0, whereas at pH 7.5 the same pattern as at pH 6.5 is
2 observed. Acetic acid reached 11,856.98 mg/L and butyric acid 1,516.42 mg/L.

3
4 Total carbohydrates removal, expressed in glucose equivalents, ranged from 70.4 to 88.3%. The highest degradation was
5 observed at pH 6.5, as shown in **Fig. 2c**. The increment of pH values was followed by an increment on the carbohydrates
6 consumption as well. Dissolved carbohydrates consumption ranged from 88.6 to 96.7%. Maximum consumption was
7 observed at pH 7.5. It is also worth mentioning that the H₂ production yield (mole of H₂ produced per mole of consumed
8 carbohydrates) reached maximum efficiency at pH 5.5, which was equal to 0.55 mol H₂/mol equivalent glucose consumed,
9 while the optimum theoretical yield is 4 mol H₂/mol equivalent glucose with acetic acid as the main end-product. Dareioti
10 et al. and Thauer et al. [9, 36] observed similar low yields as well at pH 6.0 (0.642 mol H₂/mol equivalent glucose consumed)
11 without acetic acid production at a study on the effect of pH regarding the optimization of H₂ production from agroindustrial
12 wastewaters anaerobic acidogenesis. Likewise, Stavropoulos et al. [37] reported a maximum H₂ yield at pH 5.0, reaching
13 0.84 mol H₂/mol equivalent glucose consumed, with dairy products as an easily fermentable substrate.

14
15 **Fig. 3a** depicts the concentrations of main end-products as a function of time, regarding the batch experiment that took place
16 at pH 6.0, which resulted in the maximum H₂ production. Fermentation lasted 118h and it is evident that acetic and ethanol
17 type fermentations were predominant until the 70th h, with butyric type fermentation starting to evolve from that point on
18 and then prevail by the end of experiment. Acetic acid reached a maximum of 4,140 mg/L at the 67th h of fermentation and
19 then followed a downward trend. Ethanol concentration appears to follow the same pattern as well, while butyric acid
20 concentration reached a maximum (6,016 mg/L) and appears to be stable until the end of the fermentation. Both acetic and
21 butyric acid are usually produced during fermentation processes, but their dynamics vary due to alterations of environmental
22 factors like pH, H₂ pressure and concentrations of metabolic products [38]. Hydrogen production (**Fig. 3b**) follows acetic
23 acid production trend, which is in accordance with literature [36, 38]. The maximum H₂ production is observed at 30th h
24 which remained stable during fermentation with a minor increase (1%) after the 90th h. Regarding total and dissolved
25 carbohydrates (**Fig. 3c**), their consumption is rapid until the 30th h, whereas a lower further reduction is observed, which is
26 not in line with the vast increase of the butyric acid concentration. This high concentration of butyric acid and the
27 simultaneous reduction of acetic acid, enhance the assumption that the later may be enzymatically converted to butyric acid
28 and AcCoA by butyric acid bacteria through simultaneous consumption of butyryl-CoA [39].

29 30 31 32 33 34 35 36 37 38 39 40 41 42 43 44 45 46 47 48 49 50 51 52 53 54 **3.3 Effect of pH on FVW/DN hydrolysate anaerobic fermentation**

55 Subsequent experiments, regarding the optimum pH value for maximum biohydrogen production from FVW and DN
56 hydrolysate were conducted. The feedstock in these second series of experiments consisted of FVW and DN hydrolysate
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

1 mixture at a 2:3 v/v ratio. A total of four (4) pH values were tested in the mixture, namely 6.0, 6.5, 7.0 and 7.5 due to previous
2 experiment series' findings. Hydrogen production at pH values below 5.5 was considered inadequate.

3
4 Results shown in **Fig. 4a** indicate that the highest volume of hydrogen was produced at pH 7.5 where it reached 3,021.91
5 mL and a yield of 4.02 L H₂/L_{Reactor}. The change of the feedstock nature led to a threefold increment in H₂ volume, compared
6 to FVW fermentation at a different pH value, probably due to microbial consortium enhancement from DN hydrolysate.
7
8 This is evident also from the presence of 5% CH₄ (data not shown) at pH 7.5, which is an optimum value for methanogenesis,
9 as methanogenic bacteria from the contained excreta of the used nappies could have been added in the mixture.
10

11
12 **Fig. 4c** presents the extent of carbohydrates degradation. Total carbohydrates consumption ranged from 88 to 90.5%,
13 whereas dissolved carbohydrates followed the same pattern of removal and their percentage of consumption ranged from
14 97.4 to 98.2%. Besides the microbial enhancement from the DN hydrolysate, cellulose, which is part of the total
15 carbohydrates, was also added in the mixture increasing thus the carbohydrates content of the feedstock. Concerning the
16 main end-products formation (**Fig. 4b**), results denote that the main metabolic pathways followed by the anaerobic
17 microbiota were butyric and acetic acid fermentation. Butyric acid reached a maximum (8,189.72 mg/L) at pH 6.0 and acetic
18 (7,359.35 mg/L) at pH 7.5. Ethanol was again present in all batches but seemed to decrease with the increment of pH value.
19 Lactic acid was detected at pH 6.0 and 6.5 while caproic acid showed a maximum concentration at pH 7.0 (1,009.66 mg/L).
20 Results were in accordance with other researchers as well [32, 35]. At pH 7.5, total VFAs and ethanol concentration show
21 the highest value among the experiments (17,162.19 mg/L). According to literature [40], pH values close to neutral seem to
22 enhance hydrogen consuming than hydrogen producing bacteria. However, low concentration of propionic acid, which is
23 produced from hydrogen and glucose, indicates that hydrogen producers are predominant in the microbial consortium.
24

25
26 More details about the batch experiment (pH 7.5), where maximum H₂ yield was obtained, are given in **Fig. 5**. The alteration
27 on the fermentation substrate due to DN hydrolysate addition on FVW, resulted not only at a different optimum pH value
28 for H₂ maximization, but also at a difference on the metabolic pathways followed by the microbial consortia and the final
29 concentrations of metabolic products. The fermentation of FVW/DN hydrolysate lasted 137.65 h and **Fig. 5a** presents the
30 kinetics of main end-products formation. Acetic and butyric acid are produced from the beginning of the fermentation
31 following the same trend and reaching both a concentration of 7000 mg/L after 89 h. Equal abundance of these two acids
32 has been previously reported at a pH range of 6.5-7.0 in a glucose fermentation by a mixed culture [41]. This mixed-acid
33 metabolic pathway is common, in similar waste streams fermentations i.e food waste [42]. In the present study, volatile fatty
34 acids with high molecular weight, such as caproic, and ethanol were detected at low concentrations. Propionic acid reached
35 180 mg/L after the 64th h, probably due to the presence of acidogenic bacteria such as *Corynebacteria*, *Propionibacterium*
36 and *Bifidobacterium*, which are responsible for this acid's production via transcarboxylase cycle [43]. An alternative
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

1 metabolic pathway for propionic acid formation involves the presence of lactate [43], which in our case is undetectable, and
2 is thus most probably not followed.

3
4 Carbohydrates (**Fig. 5c**) present a reduction corresponding to the rate of main end-products formation, with 60.9% of them
5 being consumed until the 20th h of fermentation, while the rest followed a slow pace reduction. Hydrogen production reached
6 a maximum at the 32.7th h and remained stable from then onwards till the completion of fermentation (**Fig. 5b**).
7
8
9

10 11 **4- CONCLUSIONS**

12 The effect of pH on the anaerobic fermentation of FVW and DN hydrolysate for bio-hydrogen production was investigated
13 in this study. Bio-hydrogen was produced efficiently and maximized by properly adjusting the pH values according to the
14 utilized fermentation substrate. For FVW, as single feedstock, the maximum H₂ yield was observed at pH 6.0 reaching 0.52
15 mol H₂/mol equivalent glucose whereas, the maximum concentration of ethanol and organic acids (15,600 mg/L) was
16 reached at pH 6.5 for the same substrate. Regarding the mixed waste stream (FVW/DN hydrolysate), both hydrogen
17 production and metabolites concentration reached a maximum at pH 7.5 with 1.12 mol H₂/mol equivalent glucose and 17,160
18 mg/L respectively. The use of FVW/DN hydrolysate instead of FVW alone, led to higher yields of H₂ and main end-products
19 of the anaerobic fermentation, as well as greater carbohydrates consumption. Although the highest H₂ production was
20 observed at pH 7.5, such pH value is not suggested for continuous operation of a fermentation system due to increased
21 possibility of converting the reactor to a methanogenic one. Moreover, the need to operate continuously at such high pH
22 value and sustain it constant, requires continuous addition of large quantities of alkaline solution, resulting thus to higher
23 operational cost than operating at suboptimal pH levels.
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40

41 **CONFLICT OF INTEREST:** The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.
42
43
44

45 **REFERENCES**

- 46
47 1. Qi, N., Hu, X., Zhao, X., Li, L., Yang, J., Zhao, Y., Li, X.: Fermentative hydrogen production with peanut shell as
48 supplementary substrate: Effects of initial substrate, pH and inoculation proportion. *Renew. Energy.* 127, 559–564
49 (2018). doi:10.1016/j.renene.2018.05.018
50
51
- 52 2. Elbeshbishy, E., Dhar, B.R., Nakhla, G., Lee, H.S.: A critical review on inhibition of dark biohydrogen
53 fermentation, (2017)
54
55
- 56 3. Yamin, J.A.A.: Comparative study using hydrogen and gasoline as fuels: Combustion duration effect. *Int. J.*
57 *Energy Res.* 30, 1175–1187 (2006). doi:10.1002/er.1213
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

4. Ghimire, A., Frunzo, L., Pirozzi, F., Trably, E., Escudie, R., Lens, P.N.L., Esposito, G.: A review on dark fermentative biohydrogen production from organic biomass: Process parameters and use of by-products, (2015)
5. Yun, Y.-M., Lee, M.-K., Im, S.-W., Marone, A., Trably, E., Shin, S.-R., Kim, M.-G., Cho, S.-K., Kim, D.-H.: Biohydrogen production from food waste: Current status, limitations, and future perspectives. *Bioresour. Technol.* 248, 79–87 (2018). doi:10.1016/J.BIORTECH.2017.06.107
6. Braguglia, C.M., Gallipoli, A., Gianico, A., Pagliaccia, P.: Anaerobic bioconversion of food waste into energy: A critical review, (2018)
7. Tawfik, A., El-Qelish, M.: Continuous hydrogen production from co-digestion of municipal food waste and kitchen wastewater in mesophilic anaerobic baffled reactor. *Bioresour. Technol.* 114, 270–274 (2012). doi:10.1016/j.biortech.2012.02.016
8. Ren, N.Q., Cao, G.L., Guo, W.Q., Wang, A.J., Zhu, Y.H., Liu, B. feng, Xu, J.F.: Biological hydrogen production from corn stover by moderately thermophile *Thermoanaerobacterium thermosaccharolyticum* W16. *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy.* 35, 2708–2712 (2010). doi:10.1016/j.ijhydene.2009.04.044
9. Dareioti, M.A., Vavouraki, A.I., Kornaros, M.: Effect of pH on the anaerobic acidogenesis of agroindustrial wastewaters for maximization of bio-hydrogen production: A lab-scale evaluation using batch tests. *Bioresour. Technol.* 162, 218–227 (2014). doi:10.1016/j.biortech.2014.03.149
10. Castelló, E., Braga, L., Fuentes, L., Etchebehere, C.: Possible causes for the instability in the H₂ production from cheese whey in a CSTR. *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy.* 43, 2654–2665 (2018). doi:10.1016/j.ijhydene.2017.12.104
11. Yeshanew, M.M., Frunzo, L., Pirozzi, F., Lens, P.N.L., Esposito, G.: Production of biohythane from food waste via an integrated system of continuously stirred tank and anaerobic fixed bed reactors. *Bioresour. Technol.* 220, 312–322 (2016). doi:10.1016/j.biortech.2016.08.078
12. Sotelo-Navarro, P.X., Poggi-Varaldo, H.M., Turpin-Marion, S.J., Vázquez-Morillas, A., Beltrán-Villavicencio, M., Espinosa-Valdemar, R.M.: Biohydrogen production from used diapers: Evaluation of effect of temperature and substrate conditioning. *Waste Manag. Res.* 35, 267–275 (2017). doi:10.1177/0734242X16677334
13. EDANA: Sustainability Report. ISBN. 2-930159–7, D/2011/5705/1 (2015). doi:http://www.sustainability.edana.org/Objects/10/Files/sustainabilityReport 2015.pdf
14. Colón, J., Ruggieri, L., Sánchez, A., González, A., Puig, I.: Possibilities of composting disposable diapers with municipal solid wastes. *Waste Manag. Res.* 29, 249–259 (2011). doi:10.1177/0734242X10364684
15. Colón, J., Mestre-Montserrat, M., Puig-Ventosa, I., Sánchez, A.: Performance of compostable baby used diapers in the composting process with the organic fraction of municipal solid waste. *Waste Manag.* 33, 1097–1103 (2013).

doi:10.1016/j.wasman.2013.01.018

- 1
2 16. Arena, U., Ardolino, F., Di Gregorio, F.: Technological, environmental and social aspects of a recycling process of
3
4 post-consumer absorbent hygiene products. *J. Clean. Prod.* 127, 289–301 (2016).
5
6 doi:10.1016/j.jclepro.2016.03.164
- 7
8 17. Cox J.-A., Druckman A., Jesson D., Mulheron M., Smyth M., T.H.: Municipal solid waste as a resource: part 2 –
9
10 case study in sustainable management. *Proc. Inst. Civ. Eng. - Waste Resour. Manag.* 168, 115–130 (2015).
11
12 doi:https://doi.org/10.1680/warm.14.00012
- 13
14 18. Durmusoglu, E., Taspinar, F., Karademir, A.: Health risk assessment of BTEX emissions in the landfill
15
16 environment. *J. Hazard. Mater.* 176, 870–877 (2010). doi:10.1016/j.jhazmat.2009.11.117
- 17
18 19. Edwards, J., Othman, M., Crossin, E., Burn, S.: Life cycle assessment to compare the environmental impact of
19
20 seven contemporary food waste management systems. *Bioresour. Technol.* 248, 156–173 (2018).
21
22 doi:10.1016/j.biortech.2017.06.070
- 23
24 20. Mohd Yasin, N.H., Rahman, N.A., Man, H.C., Mohd Yusoff, M.Z., Hassan, M.A.: Microbial characterization of
25
26 hydrogen-producing bacteria in fermented food waste at different pH values. *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy.* 36, 9571–
27
28 9580 (2011). doi:10.1016/j.ijhydene.2011.05.048
- 29
30 21. Khan, M.A., Ngo, H.H., Guo, W.S., Liu, Y., Nghiem, L.D., Hai, F.I., Deng, L.J., Wang, J., Wu, Y.: Optimization
31
32 of process parameters for production of volatile fatty acid, biohydrogen and methane from anaerobic digestion.
33
34 *Bioresour. Technol.* 219, 738–748 (2016). doi:10.1016/j.biortech.2016.08.073
- 35
36 22. Wang, J., Wan, W.: Factors influencing fermentative hydrogen production: A review, (2009)
- 37
38 23. Conway M.E., Jooste F., Smith M.D.: Treatment of absorbent sanitary paper products. *J. Clean. Prod. U.S Patent,*
39
40 (1997). doi:10.1016/S0959-6526(97)82420-1
- 41
42 24. APHA/AWWA/WEF: Standard Methods for the Examination of Water and Wastewater. *Stand. Methods.* 541
43
44 (2012). doi:ISBN 9780875532356
- 45
46 25. Joseffson, B.: Rapid spectrophotometric determination of total carbohydrates, in: K. Grasshoff, M. Ehrhardt, K.
47
48 Kremling (Eds.). *Methods Seawater Anal.* Verlag Chemie GmbH, Weinheim, Ger. 340–342 (1983)
- 49
50 26. Waterman, P.G., Mole, S.: Analysis of phenolic plant metabolites, (1994)
- 51
52 27. Kirchmann, H., Pettersson, S.: Human urine - Chemical composition and fertilizer use efficiency. *Fertil. Res.* 40,
53
54 149–154 (1994). doi:10.1007/BF00750100
- 55
56 28. Fisgativa, H., Tremier, A., Dabert, P.: Characterizing the variability of food waste quality: A need for efficient
57
58 valorisation through anaerobic digestion. *Waste Manag.* 50, 264–274 (2016). doi:10.1016/j.wasman.2016.01.041
- 59
60
61
62
63
64
65

- 1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65
29. Nguyen, D., Gadhamshetty, V., Nitayavardhana, S., Khanal, S.K.: Automatic process control in anaerobic digestion technology: A critical review, (2015)
 30. Ginkel, S. V, Sung, S., Lay, J.J.: Biohydrogen production as a function of pH and substrate concentration. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 35, 4726–4730 (2001). doi:10.1021/es001979r
 31. Chu, C.F., Li, Y.Y., Xu, K.Q., Ebie, Y., Inamori, Y., Kong, H.N.: A pH- and temperature-phased two-stage process for hydrogen and methane production from food waste. *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy.* 33, 4739–4346 (2008). doi:10.1016/j.ijhydene.2008.06.060
 32. Wang, K., Yin, J., Shen, D., Li, N.: Anaerobic digestion of food waste for volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production with different types of inoculum: Effect of pH. *Bioresour. Technol.* 161, 395–401 (2014). doi:10.1016/j.biortech.2014.03.088
 33. Wu, Y., Ma, H., Zheng, M., Wang, K.: Lactic acid production from acidogenic fermentation of fruit and vegetable wastes. *Bioresour. Technol.* 191, 53–58 (2015). doi:10.1016/j.biortech.2015.04.100
 34. Ren, N., Wang, B., Huang, J.C.: Ethanol-type fermentation from carbohydrate in high rate acidogenic reactor. *Biotechnol. Bioeng.* 54, 428–433 (1997). doi:10.1002/(SICI)1097-0290(19970605)54:5<428::AID-BIT3>3.0.CO;2-G
 35. Zhang Y.-J., Jiang J.-G., W.J.-M.: Effect of pH value on VFA concentration and composition during anaerobic fermentation of kitchen waste. *China Environ. Sci.* 33, 680–684 (2013)
 36. Thauer, R.K.K., Jungermann, K., Decker, K.: Energy conservation in chemotrophic anaerobic bacteria - ERRATUM. *Microbiol. Mol. Biol. Rev.* 41, 100–180 (1977)
 37. Stavropoulos, K.P., Kopsahelis, A., Zafiri, C., Kornaros, M.: Effect of pH on Continuous Biohydrogen Production from End-of-Life Dairy Products (EoL-DPs) via Dark Fermentation. *Waste and Biomass Valorization.* 7, 753–764 (2016). doi:10.1007/s12649-016-9548-7
 38. Khanal, S.K., Chen, W.H., Li, L., Sung, S.: Biological hydrogen production: Effects of pH and intermediate products. *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy.* 29, 1123–1131 (2004). doi:10.1016/j.ijhydene.2003.11.002
 39. Papoutsakis, E.T.: Equations and calculations for fermentations of butyric acid bacteria. *Biotechnol. Bioeng.* 67, 813–826 (2000). doi:10.1002/(SICI)1097-0290(20000320)67:6<813::AID-BIT17>3.0.CO;2-X
 40. Lee, C., Lee, S., Han, S.-K., Hwang, S.: Effect of operational pH on biohydrogen production from food waste using anaerobic batch reactors. *Water Sci. Technol.* 69, 1886–1893 (2014). doi:10.2166/wst.2014.097
 41. Fang, H.H.P., Liu, H.: Effect of pH on hydrogen production from glucose by a mixed culture. *Bioresour. Technol.* 82, 87–93 (2002). doi:10.1016/S0960-8524(01)00110-9

42. Jiang, J., Zhang, Y., Li, K., Wang, Q., Gong, C., Li, M.: Volatile fatty acids production from food waste: Effects of pH, temperature, and organic loading rate. *Bioresour. Technol.* 143, 525–530 (2013).
doi:10.1016/j.biortech.2013.06.025
43. Zhou, M., Yan, B., Wong, J.W.C., Zhang, Y.: Enhanced volatile fatty acids production from anaerobic fermentation of food waste: A mini-review focusing on acidogenic metabolic pathways. *Bioresour. Technol.* 248, 68-78 (2018) doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2017.06.121

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

FIGURE AND TABLE CAPTIONS

1
2
3 **Fig. 1** a) Schematic diagram of batch experimental methodology for FVW and DN hydrolysate, b) Experimental apparatus
4 for the batch tests process

5
6
7 **Fig. 2** a) H₂, CO₂ and specific volumetric hydrogen evolution at STP conditions, b) Main end-products, c) removal of total
8 (t-CH) and dissolved (d-CH) carbohydrates and H₂ production yield per mole of consumed carbohydrates expressed in
9 glucose equivalents, at the pH values tested for FVW anaerobic fermentation

10
11
12
13 **Fig. 3** a) Main end-products, b) biogas, H₂ and CO₂ volume at STP conditions, c) degradation of total (t-CH) and dissolved
14 (d-CH) carbohydrates expressed in glucose equivalents, as a function of experimental time at the optimum pH value
15 (6.0) for FVW anaerobic fermentation

16
17
18
19 **Fig. 4** a) H₂, CO₂ and specific volumetric hydrogen evolution at STP conditions, b) Main end-products, c) removal of total
20 (t-CH) and dissolved (d-CH) carbohydrates and H₂ production yield per mole of consumed carbohydrates expressed in
21 glucose equivalents, at the pH values tested for FVW/DN hydrolysate anaerobic fermentation

22
23
24
25 **Fig. 5** a) Main end-products, b) biogas, H₂ and CO₂ volume at STP conditions, c) degradation of total (t-CH) and dissolved
26 (d-CH) carbohydrates expressed in glucose equivalents, as a function of experimental time at the optimum pH value
27 (7.5) for FVW/DN hydrolysate anaerobic fermentation

28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35 **Table 1:** Chemical composition of fermentation substrates used in this study. Data are mean values (n=3, ± SD)

(a)

(b)

FIG. 1

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 2

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 3

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 4

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 5

Table 1

Physicochemical parameter	FVW (g/kg ww)	DN hydrolysate (g/L)	Mixture (2:3 v/v) (g/L)
pH	3.48 (0.30)	7.73 (0.04)	4.67 (0.18)
Moisture (%)	88.85 (0.40)	99.19 (0.10)	96.72 (0.31)
t-Carbohydrates*	64.53 (7.46)	1.37 (0.13)	28.40 (2.15)
d-Carbohydrates*	46.93 (1.41)	0.24 (0.01)	23.04 (3.39)
Phenols**	0.99 (0.02)	0.04 (0.00)	0.35 (0.01)
t-COD	103.77 (22.08)	5.87 (1.26)	42.11 (1.67)
d-COD	72.39 (4.71)	1.51 (0.22)	23.97 (0.49)
Fats and Oils	0.63 (0.07)	0.06 (0.01)	0.49 (0.01)
t-Phosphorus	0.34 (0.03)	0.02 (0.00)	0.12 (0.00)
d-Phosphorus	0.28 (0.02)	0.02 (0.00)	0.10 (0.00)
TKN	1.54 (0.13)	0.26 (0.02)	0.75 (0.06)
NH ₃ -N	0.36 (0.07)	0.26 (0.02)	0.12 (0.01)
TSS	39.83 (5.97)	4.45 (0.18)	14.20 (0.71)
VSS	39.00 (4.58)	4.30 (0.32)	13.93 (0.63)
TS	111.55 (3.99)	8.07 (0.97)	32.83 (3.07)
VS	101.03 (3.72)	4.99 (0.98)	29.30 (2.80)

*In glucose equivalent

**In syringic acid equivalent

